

Damage ratings of selected cultivars to BPH biotype 2 in the SSST and MSST, IRRI.

IRRI accession no.	Variety	Damage rating ^a	
		SSST	MSST
4907	Birado	MR	R
4914	Toma 112	S	MR
4936	Ngasein thidat	S	S
5216	Mantika	S	S
5837	MTU14	S	R
5856	DA26	S	S
5886	Ngathalun CWR 10/9	S	S
5955	Hin trang	S	S
6002	Guttikusma	S	R
6008	Radin Siak 34	S	R
6029	Ptb 17	S	MR
6039	AKP8	S	S
6066	Bilugyun C32-1	S	S
6068	D52-37	S	S
6114	Molagasamba 18	MR	R
6145	MTU7	S	R
6162	American HS 1	S	R
6274	Ptb 9	MR	R
6291	Ptb 8	S	R
6339	BAM12	S	R
6353	MO 1	S	R
(R check)	IR60	R	R
(R check)	ASD7	MR	R
(MR check)	Triveni	S	MR
(S check)	IR26	S	S

^a R = resistant with rating of 1-3, MK = moderately resistant with rating of 5, and S = susceptible with rating of 7-9.

BPH biotype 2 population growth. Ten newly hatched nymphs were used to infest 25-d-old potted plants in a mylar film cage. BPH progeny per cage was counted at 35 DI.

Nine varieties were susceptible in both tests; 11 were susceptible in SSST but moderately resistant or resistant in MSST; and 4 were moderately resistant in SSST and resistant in MSST. Plant damage ratings of some varieties in SSST increased together, indicating insignificant differences in resistance (Fig. 1). In the MSST, the damage ratings of those varieties were significantly different, and older and younger plants had different resistance levels.

MO 1, Guttikusma, BAM12, MTU7, and MTU14, which were susceptible in SSST but resistant in MSST, have different levels of antibiosis, as shown by lower BPH population growth than in susceptible IR26 (Fig. 2). Antibiosis in those cultivars is apparently a factor that is measured in MSST but not in SSST.

MSST is a fast screening technique

1. Plant damage rating of rice varieties on SSST at indicated days after infestation with BPH biotype 2.

that can be used to mass screen varieties at tillering. Resistance at this stage is expected to be influenced by minor genes and increases with age. MSST, therefore, may identify more durable resistance than SSST, which identifies the major gene for resistance. *ℓ*

2. Varieties susceptible to BPH in MSST but resistant in SSST. IR60 is the resistant check; IR26, the susceptible check.

Mahaveera: a gall midge (GM)-resistant rice for coastal Karnataka

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Mahaveera (IET2886/Annapurna) was released for cultivation in coastal

Karnataka, where it will replace GMR 17 in transplanted uplands. Mahaveera (KKP 2) matures in 110 d and yields 4.1 t/ha, 37% more than GMR 17. Grains are long, bold, red kerneled, and suitable for parboiling, with 72% hulling. It is GM resistant, with 0.02% silvershoots compared to 33% for susceptible Annapurna and 4% for GMR 17 (see table). *ℓ*

GM incidence and yield performance of Mahaveera, 1979-83, Mandya, India.

Year	Silvershoots (%)			Yield (t/ha)		
	Mahaveera	Annapurna	GMR17	Mahaveera	Annapurna	GMR17
1979	0	32	1	4.3	3.3	3.5
1980	0	54	12	4.9	3.3	3.3
1981	0.1	30	4	4.4	3.4	3.5
1982	0	22	9	4.4	3.4	3.5
1983	0	28	5	2.7	1.9	1.6
Mean	0.02	33	6	4.1	3.1	3.0